

Greener Journal of Physical Sciences

ISSN: 2276-7851 ICV 2012: 5.88

Analysis of Vulnerability to Flood Disaster in Kano State, Nigeria

By

Aliyu Baba Nabegu

Research Article

Analysis of Vulnerability to Flood Disaster in Kano State, Nigeria

Aliyu Baba Nabegu

Department of Geography, Kano University of Science and Technology, Wudil.

Email: aliyunabegu@kustwudil.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study assesses the vulnerability of households to flood in Kano state, Nigeria, using questionnaires survey, infrastructure analysis and flood impact information of the most recent flood disaster collected by the Federal and State agencies responsible for disaster management. The survey covered households in areas that had experienced heavy damage (Zone 1), medium (Zone 2) and light damage (Zone 3). One hundred and fifty respondents from each zone were interviewed in face-to-face interaction between March and April 2013. The questionnaire explored household characteristics before and after the flood disaster, different coping mechanisms and analysis of infrastructures such as schools, roads, bridges, hospitals and markets. The human security index was used to determine the time a household will need to recover from property damage. To determine the strength of resilience of each of the zones, the coping strategy with the highest score were summed up and then divided by the total number of indicated coping measures in each zone to obtain an index of the relative strength of coping measures at each zone. A vulnerability index was also calculated for each zone. The results indicate variations between the zones in coping strength and vulnerability which implies varying local coping capacities. The study recommends the need to collect more baseline data on vulnerability to flood at the local level which will ease preparedness and management of flood disaster in the state.

Keywords: Vulnerability Index, hazard, human security index, disaster, risk, coping capacity.

INTRODUCTION

The frequency and severity with which flood disasters occur is on the increase in many regions of the world (Figure, 1). Nigeria is no exception as in 2012, it experienced an unprecedented flood disaster that affected half of the 36 states including Kano, with 21 million people displaced; 597,476 houses destroyed or damaged; over 363 people killed and an estimated loss of USD 19.6 billion (NEMA, 2013). It has also been predicted that 70% of Nigeria's 36 states are at risk from flooding in 2013 (NIMET, 2013). Consequently, there has been an increase in recognition by both governments and multilateral agencies of the need to mainstream flood risk reduction into development plans. Nigeria's (2003) agenda 21 document spelt out objectives to combat floods which include providing a master plan for flood control and relief measures for victims; mitigate floods through the relevant land use laws and edicts; improve institutional capacity for flood prediction and public awareness programmes and minimize the impact of floods through the provision and maintenance of appropriate infrastructure.

Figure 1: Combined trends in the number of disasters events and related consequences.

Source: The OFDA/CRED International Disasters Database (EM-DAT) (Adapted from Green (2004) and Dilley et al. (2005).

However, governments in Nigeria have consistently failed to systematically treat risk reduction from floods as an integrated, cross-sectoral objective. Instead, they have dealt with flood risk primarily within the very narrow framework of flood control, improved preparedness, relief and rehabilitation and preparedness capabilities and expose support to affected groups, consequently, flood hazards continue to cause great damage to infrastructure and loss of life.

Furthermore, although international databases on disasters such as the database of the Centre for Research on Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED), exist, their application for vulnerability measurement is limited by the fact that the data does not give sufficient information to assess the various vulnerabilities at different spatial levels and units and also the fact that reported damages predominantly focus on direct costs and losses, often excluding indirect losses such as the long-term socio-economic impacts of a disaster (Benson, 2004). Additionally, the different definitions of the categories used in these statistics, such as "affected" or "injury" are a complication when trying to make comparisons and analysis (Wisner et al., 2004). Moreover, although government disaster managers are generally aware of the propensity of many flood disaster scenarios in Kano state and indeed Nigeria, the fact that their occurrence and consequences are often sudden, random and not well predicted creates difficulty in getting the appropriate response. This makes analysis of the vulnerability at local level necessary in order to identify weak points needing special attention during disaster situations. This paper assesses the vulnerability of local communities to flood in Kano state by analyzing the susceptibility and coping capacity of households and infrastructures.

METHODOLOGY

Kano state was divided into three zones based on the degree of damage in each location based on flood impact information, collected by state emergency management agency (SEMA) and the federally controlled Nigeria emergency management agency (NEMA) after the disaster. Consequently, the survey covered households in areas that had experienced heavy damage (zone 1), medium damage (zone 2) and light damage (zone 3) as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: The study locations.

One hundred and fifty respondents selected from each zone were interviewed in face-to-face interaction during a four-week period between March and April 2013. The questionnaire explored household characteristics before and after the flood disaster and their different coping mechanisms. The analysis of the vulnerability of infrastructures involved assessment of schools, hospitals, roads, bridges and markets. To determine the strength of resilience of the zones, the coping strategy with the highest score at the household level were summed up and then divided by the total number of indicated coping measures in each zone to obtain an index of the relative strength of coping measures at each zone. A risk index was calculated with the calculated coping strength of the zones and hazard occurrences using the UNDP (1992) formula:

$$\text{Vulnerability} = \frac{\text{Hazard}}{\text{Coping strategies}}$$

Study Area

Kano state is located between longitudes 7° 45' E and 10° 35' E, and between latitudes 10° 30' N and 13° 00' N. The climate is the tropical dry-and-wet type, with mean annual rainfall between 800 mm in the north and 1100 mm in the south.

Study locations

Zone 1 (Fagge)

This is a suburb of Kano metropolis. It is highly urbanized with population density in excess of 1000 per hectare. Housing is unregulated with substantial part made of very old and sub-standard construction. The area is traversed by the Gogau stream which has now been turned into a gutter due to settlement along its historic flood plain. The river is the major cause of flooding in the area. The practice of dumping municipal waste into the river channel accentuates the flood hazard. Drainages in most of the area are stalled and where it is visible has either been built upon or clogged by dirt and household waste. Annual rainfall is between 550 -800 mm spread over 5 months.

Zone 2 - (Bichi)

This is a semi urban settlement. It has a mixture of modern and traditional building. Housing and town planning is virtually nonexistent. The drainages cover only a limited part of the settlement and most of which is clogged by municipal waste. Building type consist of modern and traditional with substantial part substandard. Annual rainfall is between 400 - 650 mm spread over 4 months.

Zone 3 (Tudunwada)

It is a semi urban settlement located to the south of the state. Many rivers traverse the area. The soil is well drained and surrounding area is vegetated. There is no town and housing planning as in other areas of the state. The drainage is often encroached upon by settlement or clogged by dirt and municipal waste. Annual rainfall is between 1000 to 1200 mm spread over 7 months.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact of last Disaster in the three zones

Table 1 shows the data on the impact of the last flood disaster from the three zones. Damage to property appears to be a common feature in all three zones attesting to the fact that housing in all areas cannot withstand flood. According to The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of the United States the data needed for assessing the vulnerability of housing includes structural integrity, construction type and quality, age, size, types of materials and impacts the materials might have on environmental resources. The analysis of housing damage in the three zones showed that 51.9 % of houses were destroyed or seriously damaged in the disaster, however further evaluation showed that of the houses built of mud, only 0.9% survived, 82% were destroyed and 12.1% damaged compared to those made with concrete, where 48% survived, 11.2% damaged and only 2.7% destroyed in the three zones. It has been shown that the adaptive capacity of a community can be defined as the vulnerability of a society before disaster strikes and its resilience after (Wisner et al., 2004) and that the adaptive capacity is not "exogenous", but related to its level of development. Unfavourable economic and social conditions such as poor urban infrastructures and services and weak regulatory practices including poor enforcement of building standards can render a society much more vulnerable and less resilient to any given shock (Davidson, 1995; Bollin et al., 2003). Given the limited scope for diversifying against flood risks at the household level as a result of poverty which is accentuated by weak enforcement of planning and housing regulations due to corruption and substandard construction, flood in Kano state are always a disaster with deadly consequences.

Table 1: Impact of last Disaster in the three zones

Location	Types of Hazards				
	Injury	Loss of Life	Loss of livelihood	Damage of property	Displacement
Zone 3	3	8	30	20	15
Zone 2	7	10	35	22	18
Zone 1	8	17	40	22	25

Source: Fieldwork, 2013

For instance in zone 1, most of the houses that were damaged completely were areas that were affected in 2008, located in areas that were declared risk zones and house owners were compensated by government to move to safer areas but remained in the same locations. To reduce the vulnerability, it is important for governments to monitor and enforce building codes and standards. Resilience can be enhanced also by implementing measures that would lower the cost of relief delivery such as improved communications and preparing adequate contingency plans for rapid responses. Other measures could include increase in human capital and physical assets that can reduce the level of poverty.

Infrastructures are systems with great importance for society that, if disrupted, impact various supply chains that leads to further dramatic consequences (BMI, 2005). Infrastructure sectors in Kano state include electric power, roads, bridges, hospitals and schools. Damage to infrastructures is second to housing in all three zones especially electricity poles which were the most severely affected with 69% completely destroyed, followed by roads 18%, schools 13 % and hospitals 9%. Analysis shows that in zone 1, 50 per cent of the hospitals, 20% of the bridges and 13% of the schools were damaged or destroyed. The damage to infrastructure not only exacerbate impact of flood disasters, but also creates problems in the evacuations of the affected population and because of the interrelationship between the infrastructures and other sectors of the economy, also disrupts socio-economic activities leading to loss of livelihood as well as scarce resources to coping with reconstruction. Consequently, it can be concluded that the resistance, resilience and susceptibility of the infrastructure determine the degree of their vulnerability as well as that of the community in which they are situated.

Data from the disaster management agencies at the state and federal levels indicate that on average it takes 24- 43 months to repair electricity poles and reconnect electricity, whereas repairs to roads and bridges takes 18 - 56 months. With regards to schools and hospitals it takes 9 - 16 months. In areas where relocation of houses was proposed the period takes between 48 -to 60 months. Although, the significance of a reliable functioning infrastructure and the negative consequence of their disruptions are recognized in this study, considerable time is spent to remedy damages as a result of bureaucracy and corruption. Consequently, even though local communities have their own coping strategies reliable infrastructure can reduce vulnerability significantly.

With respect to death and injury there appeared to be clear variation between the zones. The analysis of the data of the dead revealed that the age groups from 0 to 9 years as well as the age groups over 40 years were highly vulnerable to the flood, respectively suffering 25 % and 44% of all casualties. With regard to the absolute number of dead, the young age group shows the most fatalities. However, the relative number of dead of specific age groups showed that elderly people were especially vulnerable. For example, the fatality rate among people aged 70~80 years was around 40%, and in the 50-60-years age group, 13%. In contrast the fatality rate among those in their thirties was only 2 %.

Gender too played a role regarding the dead as nearly twice as many females 72% as males 28% were dead, clearly showing that females are more vulnerable to flood than men. In addition to their physical weakness, female might also be more exposed due to their traditional role of carrying out activities around the house. The enormous gender gap between the revealed vulnerability of females and males regarding the likelihood of being killed by flood was also observed in other studies of flood affected areas, for example in the Aceh province in Indonesia (Oxfam, 2005; Rofi et al., 2006) and in the Tamil Nadu province in India (Guha-Sapir et al., 2006).

Analysis of the vulnerability of households with regard to loss of livelihood also shows clear variation. Similar pattern is reflected in the number of displaced households reflecting the impact of poverty and physiographic factors (Nabegu, 2013). However, elsewhere, it has been shown that where the standard of living is broadly similar in all parts of an area as is the case in this study, indicators like the illiteracy rate or the GDP are not useful. (Hidajat et al., 2003; Dwyer et al., 2004). Tapsell et al. (2002) have identified indicators reflecting social vulnerability that consist of an index; the elderly aged 75+, lone parents, and those with pre-existing health problems and financial deprivation.

To measure the vulnerability of different social groups to flood, the human Security Index proposed by Plate (2002) was used to measure the time a household will need to recover from property damage. The damage and the respective reconstruction costs were based on four damage categories: "damaged totally" (N500, 000), "damaged partially, cannot be used" (N250, 000). "Damaged partially" (N100, 000) and "minor damage" at (N50, 000) and the time that the household would need to repair its housing damage assuming that it would spend all its disposable income for the activity only. Table 2 revealed that, in zone 1 , 11 % will not able to replace their

losses using their own financial capacity, while for zone 2, 21% and 30.9% in zone 3 will not be able to recover, showing clearly a marked variation in the ability to recover among the three zones. Among those households that were able to replace losses they had suffered, 6% did not suffer any damage in zone 1, and thus needed zero days to replace the losses, while 12% of the households were able to repair or replace their housing damage within one year in the same zone.

Table 2: Time that households need to replace housing damage

Status	Zone1	Zone 2	Zone 3
No damage	6.0%	5.0%	3.1%
Up to 12 months	12.0%	10%	8.0%
12 – 24 months	12.0%	9.0%	7.0%
More than 2 years	59.0%	55%	51%
Not able to recover at all	11.0%	21 %	30.9%

Source: Fieldwork, 2013

The data also indicated that 12 % of the households would require more than two years in the same zone, in contrast, 60% of the households would not be able to recover unaided within two years. Thus twice as many households need external financial support to repair the actual housing damage. This number could be even higher considering the expected general decline in income after the flood due to collapse of infrastructure, damage to the livelihood and general disruption to socio-economic activities. It must be noted that other factors, not only the exposure and actual damage are significant in determining the ability to recover, such as the size of the household; the age structure and the job diversity are important factors and determine the differences in the ability to recover. The combination of these factors can be valuable in estimating and identifying the most vulnerable groups and areas.

Coping Capacity

The reported coping mechanisms against flood from the three zones are shown in Table 3. The three main strategies were selling of assets seeking paid employment and migration respectively. Clearly, floods have major impacts on the socio-economic well being of households in developing countries, whether in the rural or urban informal sectors as they are often overwhelmed by shocks that include unemployment, loss of livelihood, assets, injury, death, disease etc., which leads to immediate hardships that compel household to make decisions with serious long term consequences. Though these decisions might reduce exposure to the shock, they often as well disrupt long-term livelihood referred to as “consumption smoothing by income smoothing”.

The variation between the zones, especially the level of local economic prosperity helps to strengthen resilience even in poor rural setting. In terms of how people coped with the disaster, social assets consisting of networks relationships of trust and reciprocity, and access to wider institutions in society has been shown to play important roles (Carney, 1998).

Table 3: Coping Strategy for Flood in the three Zones

Location	Types of Coping Strategies							
	Find Paid employment	Migrate to city	Sale assets	Send children/women to domestic work	Send children to school(informal)	Borrow money	Beg	Lease assets
Zone 1	15	18	20	13	8	10	4	5
Zone 2	13	17	19	15	9	10	5	2
Zone 3	13	18	20	14	10	11	5	1

Source: Fieldwork, 2013

There were no recognized local organization in all the three zones as such none of the affected households gained financial assistance from local organizations to recover from this catastrophe. However, assistance came from neighbors (35%), friends (10%), other family members and relatives (55%) that first came to help the affected people. It is thus clear that informal social networks play an important role in coping. The response from the local sates and federal government when it came arrived weeks after the disaster.

Traditionally disasters were viewed as isolated natural events, and few linkages were made to the circumstances of the people affected. Technical solutions prevailed, and the relief and rehabilitation measures that were normally taken were intended to restore pre-disaster conditions (Schmuck-Widman,1996;Winchester,1992). In order to promote prevention and avoid decisions based on risk perception ,

the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 1998) conceived the idea of creating an index based on a quantitative approach that would allow for comparisons between countries and an index is to identify a country's social and economic vulnerabilities, along with hazards caused by natural conditions and human activities that contribute to the risk was therefore developed.

However, evidence suggested that vulnerability was not homogeneous in "communities", but varied widely, led to a move towards development of a local index. Consequently, in order to determine level of coping strength and obtain a cross-level value for each zone, the coping strategy with the highest score at the household level were summed up and then divided by the total number of the indicated coping measure to obtain an index showing the relative strength of coping measure in each zone. These indices are shown in Table 4. These indices provide the coping strength in each zone which can be used to compare the strengths of coping measures across the zones which range from 24.4 - 70, with zone 2 having the highest value and zone1 the lowest. A measure of the local coping index is significant because, communities are knowledgeable about their own environment. They are rich in experience of coping with emergencies and community coping methods have evolved over time and demonstrated that they are best suited to the local economic, cultural and political environment.

Table 4: The relative strength of coping measure to flood in the three zones

Manageability	Zone		
	1	2	3
Coping strategy	24.44	69.51	51.04

Source: Fieldwork, 2013

Interventions with community participation have the potential to positively address general socio-economic concerns. Participation will empower the community with new knowledge and skills and develop the leadership capability of community members, and so strengthen their capacity to contribute to development initiatives.

Vulnerability Index

Table 5 shows the vulnerability index for three major hazards recorded and shows that in case of flood, Zone 1 has the highest coping capacity followed by zone 3 and zone 2 has the least, but, Zone 3 is the most vulnerable to flood (0.38), and closely followed by Zone 2 (0.31) and the least is Zone 1 (0.16). However, though flood occurrence is highest in Zone 2 (38.94), this zone's vulnerability is only second highest because it has a relatively *low* coping capacity of 66.37 compared to Zone 3, 75.99 which implies higher flood manageability capacities. The other zones have essentially low flood vulnerability because they have low flood occurrence and high manageability capacities.

The vulnerability index identifies the social and economic vulnerabilities, along with hazards caused by flood that contribute to the risk in the locality and has been used successfully in the last few years due to the growing evidence that prevailing top down approaches in disaster risk management has led to inequitable and unsustainable results.

Table: 5 Flood Vulnerability Index of the three Zones

	Zones		
	1	2	3
Coping ability	77.78	66.37	75.99
Risk/Hazard occurrence	31.06	38.94	30.00
Vulnerability index	0.16	0.31	0.38

Source: Fieldwork, 2013

Many such programmes fail to address the specific local needs of vulnerable communities, ignore the potential of local resources and capacities, and in some cases even increase people's social and economic vulnerability.

CONCLUSION

The ability to measure vulnerability to flood is an essential prerequisite for reducing its risk, but it requires an ability to both identify and better understand exactly what are the various vulnerability to flood hazard that largely determine risk in Kano state. Because vulnerability to flood is multidimensional, it requires a reduction of potentially gatherable data to a set of important indicators and criteria that facilitate an estimation of vulnerability. Although many activities relating to risk and vulnerability assessment are currently undertaken, only a few of these approaches actually focus on the measurement of local risk and the specific local needs of vulnerable communities. The measurement of vulnerability to flood in this study was aimed at identifying the capacities of households and local communities to manage and overcome emergencies and disasters situations. One of the main foci identified in this study is the need to determine the most vulnerable population groups within the society and thus support their preparedness for disaster situations. Assessment and knowledge about the possible vulnerabilities of critical infrastructure is also essential for averting major dangers that can influence local well being.

REFERENCES

- Benson, C. (2004) Macro-economic Concepts of Vulnerability: Dynamics, Complexity and Public Policy, in G. Bankoff, G. Frerks and D. Hilhorst, eds, *Mapping Vulnerability: Disasters, Development and People*, London: Earthscan.
- Bollin, C.C. Cardenas, H. H. and Vatsa, K.S. (2003) Natural Disasters Net Work: Comprehensive Risk Management by Communities and Local Governments, Washington D.C.: Inter-American Development Bank, available from the GTZ Advisory Project's homepage www.gtz.de/disaster-reduction, English: <http://www.gtz.de/disaster-reduction/english>.
- Bundesministerium des Innern (BMI) (2005) Schutz Kritischer Infrastructure Basisschutzkonzept. Empfehlungen für Unternehmen. Berlin: BMI, available at http://www.bmi.bund.de/cIn_012/nn_22688/Internet/Content/Common/atlagen/Broschueren/2005/Basiskonzept_kritische_Infrastrukturen, templateId=raw property=publication File.pdf/Basiskonzept_kritische_Infrastrukturen/.
- Carney, D. (1998) Implementing the Sustainable Rural Livelihoods Approach, in D. Carney, ed., *Sustainable Rural Livelihoods: What Contribution Can We Make*, London: Department for International Development (DFID).
- Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED) Website, available at <http://www.cred.be/>
- Davidson, R. (1995) An Urban Earthquake Disaster Risk Index, Report No. 121, Stanford: The John A. Blume Earthquake Engineering Center.
- Dwyer, A., Zoppou, C., Nielsen, O. S., Day, and Roberts, S. (2004) Quantifying Social Vulnerability: A Methodology for Identifying Those at Risk to Natural Hazards, *Geosciences Australia Record* 2004/14, available at http://www.ga.gov.au/image_cache/GA4267
- Dilley, M., Chen, R.S., Deichmann, U., Lerner-Lam, A.L., Arnold, M., (2005) Natural Disaster Hotspots: A Global Risk Analysis. The World Bank, US, 150 pp...
- Green, C. (2004) The Evaluation of Vulnerability to Flooding, *Disaster Prevention and Management* 13(4): 323-329.
- Guha-Sapir, D., Parry, L.V. O., Degomme, P.C., Joshi, J.P., Saulina, A (2006) "Risk Factors for Mortality and Injury: Post-Tsunami Epidemiological Findings from Tami Nadu", Draft Report, Brussels: Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED).
- Hidajat, R (2002) Merapi/Java: Fluch und Segen eines Vulkans. In *Geographische Rundschau* 1/2002. Braunschweig.
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Coastal Services Centre (no date) Risk and Vulnerability Assessment Steps. Environmental Analysis Risk and Vulnerability Assessment Tool (RVA T), available at <http://www.csc.noaa.gov/rvatjenvienv.html>.
- Nabegu, A.B (2013) Assessing Household Vulnerability to Natural Disaster in Kano State Paper presented at the Annual Conference of the Association of Nigerian Geographers Held between 4th to 8th November, 2013, at the Department of Geography, University of Maiduguri
- Nigeria's Agenda 21 Report (2003) The Ministry of Environment, Federal Republic of Nigeria, Abuja.
- Nigeria Emergency Management Agency NEMA (2013) Flood Disaster report 2012, Daily Trust Newspaper, 11th May, 2012
- Nigeria Meteorological Agency NIMET (2013) 2013 Rainfall Prediction, Daily Trust, March 11th 2013

- Oxfam (2005) The Tsunami's Impact on Women, Oxfam Briefing Note, Oxford, available at http://www.oxfam.org.uk/what_we_do/issues/conflict_disasters/downloads/bn_tsunami_women.pdf.
- Plate, E.J (2002) "Towards Development of a Human Security Index", in: E.J. Plate, ed., *Environment and Human Security: Contributions to a Workshop in Bonn*. 23-25 October 2002, Germany, pp. 13/1-13/13.
- Rofi, A., Doocy S., Robinson, R. C (2006) Tsunami Mortality and Displacement in Aceh Province", Indonesia, *Disasters*
- Schmuck-Widmann, H (1996) Living with the Floods: Survival Strategies of Char dwellers in Bangladesh, Berlin: FDCL.
- Tapsell, S.M., Penning-Rowsell, E.C., Tunstall, S.M. Wilson, T.L. (2002) Vulnerability to Flooding: Health and Social Dimensions", in *Phil. Trans. R. soc. Land. A*. 360, pp. 511-525.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (1998) Guidelines for Community Vulnerability Analysis: An Approach for Pacific Island Countries, Geneva: UNDP, available at: http://www.proventionconsortiuOl.org/files/tools_CRA/UNDP_eVA.pdf.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (1992) An Overview of Disaster Management, 2nd edn, Washington, D.C.: UNDP
- Winchester, P (1992) Power, Choice, and Vulnerability: Case Study in Mismanagement in South India, London: James and James Science Publishers.
- Wisner. B. P., Blaikie, T Cannon, D (2004) *At Risk: Natural Hazards. People's Vulnerability, and Disasters*, 2nd edn, London: Routledge.